

Background

- Rising CO₂ emission, global temperature increase, and sea level rise highlight the urgent need for climate education.
- Public reluctance to transition from fossil fuels suggests a gap in understanding energy consumption environmental and social impacts.
- Misconceptions about solutions (e.g., electric vehicles) reveal a need for deeper discussions on systemic challenges and sustainability.
- Many schools do not equip students with the critical-thinking skills needed to assess environmental challenges and develop solutions.
- These topics are often taught in isolation, limiting interdisciplinary connections.
- Education is key to fostering understanding and encouraging environmentally friendly choices.

Objectives

- Develop interactive and research-backed learning modules to enhance climate literacy through experiential learning.
- Engage K-12 students, educators, college students, and community members with hands-on, outdoor, and virtual activities.
- Foster understanding of human activities, energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, and climate trends.
- Empower future generations to make informed energy choices.
- Bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world problem-solving.
- Support the transition to a more sustainable and low-carbon future.

Methods

- Developed interactive modules on climate change, air quality, renewable energy, and low-carbon communities.
- Included hands-on, outdoor, and virtual activities for comprehensive learning.
- Conducted research using academic and government sources.
- Identified educational activities through targeted online searches.
- Created presentations with visuals, background information, and interactive elements.
- Integrated discussion questions to enhance engagement.

Results

- Module 1: Climate Change - Interactive activities include ice cap melting (elementary), greenhouse gas trapping (intermediate), and sea-level rise simulations (college), with discussions to assess understanding.
- Module 2: Air Quality Monitoring - Hands-on experiments with air quality monitors (elementary), acid rain simulations (intermediate), and smog creation (college) to explore air pollution effects.
- Module 3: Renewable Energy - Wind (buildable turbine), solar (DIY panel), and tidal (makeshift dam) activities, with discussions on feasibility.
- Module 4: Low Carbon Communities - Recap of previous modules, brainstorming local renewable energy solutions, and discussions on clean energy challenges and global initiatives.

Learning Modules Presentation

Presentation at Glassboro High School

Tidal Energy Experience at Rancocas Creek

Presentation at the Teen Tech event at Atlantic Cape Community College

Summary

- Developed research-backed learning modules to enhance climate literacy through experiential learning.
- Activities designed for K-12 students, educators, college students, and community members.
- Relationships focused among human activities, energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, and climate change impacts.

Summary

- Simulations on ice cap melting, greenhouse gas trapping, and sea-level rise to illustrate climate change effects.
- Activities using air quality monitors, acid rain simulations, and smog creation to enhance understanding of air pollution.
- Hands-on activities with wind turbines, solar panels, and tidal energy models to explore renewable energy solutions.

Future Work

- Expanding research on the transition to renewable energy liability and efficiency and field experimentation for air quality.
- Developing more integrated modules within depth teachings.
- Covering more diverse groups of students and communities to raise the awareness and encourage them in adapting the use of renewable energy and helping mitigate the climate change.

References

1. US EPA, O. (2015, December 16). *Climate Change Indicators: Greenhouse Gases* [Reports and Assessments]. <https://www.epa.gov/climate-indicators/greenhouse-gases>
2. Ritchie, H., Rosado, P., & Roser, M. (2023). CO₂ and Greenhouse Gas Emissions. *Our World in Data*. <https://ourworldindata.org/co2-and-greenhouse-gas-emissions>
3. *Causes of climate change—European Commission*. (n.d.). Retrieved September 9, 2024, from https://climate.ec.europa.eu/climate-change/causes-climate-change_en
4. *Causes—NASA Science*. (n.d.). Retrieved September 9, 2024, from <https://science.nasa.gov/climate-change/causes/>
5. *Five Ways Climate Change Will Affect You: Wild Weather*. (n.d.). Retrieved September 9, 2024, from <http://www.nationalgeographic.com/climate-change/how-to-live-with-it/weather.html>

Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the USEPA for funding this project. Thanks to Dr. Kauser Jahan and the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering at Rowan University for continuing support.

Contact Information

Jillian Jankowski – jankow58@students.rowan.edu
Payton Keblish - keblis62@students.rowan.edu
Aleksandra Dukleski - dukles43@rowan.edu
Philip Sedalis – sedali25@students.rowan.edu
Zhiming Zhang – zhangz@rowan.edu